

Synthesis of Steroidal Alkaloids and Sapogenins*

S. V. Kessar

(Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh)

It is indeed a great honour for me to be called upon to deliver the Basudev Banerjee Memorial lecture. First of all I will like to pay my respectful homage to late Dr. Banerjee for his qualities of head and heart so deeply cherished by those who had the privilege of coming in contact with him. I also wish to express my gratitude to Indian Chemical Society for providing me this opportunity to present our work on steroidal sapogenins and solanum alkaloids.

We have focussed our attention on three structural types of naturally occurring steroidal compounds, namely spirostanes, spirosolanes and solanidanes. Diosgenin (XXVIII), solasodine (LXIII) and solanidine (XLVI) may be considered typical representatives of these families, although each comprises of a large number of members exhibiting diverse structural variations. These compounds have attracted considerable attention because of their intriguing chemistry and as sources for steroidal wonder drugs. Prodigous amount of work has been undertaken on their degradation, inter-relation and structural elucidation¹. In contrast, very little could be accomplished in the line of synthesis. Only in the beginning of the present decade Sondheimer, Danieli and Mazur² achieved synthesis of tigogenin from epiandrosterone by a masterly twenty step sequence. While the present work was in progress Schreiber and coworkers reported some excellent syntheses³ and inter-conversions in the field of solanum alkaloids. However, routes of both the groups are limited, either to alkaloids or to sapogenins, and leave something to be desired in terms of flexibility and steric control. Selective entry into 25R or S series is not possible and many members, specially those with a Δ^5 bond or ring F functions, are not directly accessible. The aim of our investigation was to develop a versatile and stereospecific route to steroidal alkaloids and sapogenins. Further, in view of their biogenetic and structural correlation it was hoped that it will be possible to build up all the three types from a common intermediate. Fortunately, these objectives have been realised as will be clear from the sequel. In addition, many points of mechanistic and theoretical interest came up, some of which we have tried to investigate in depth.

The key step in the envisaged scheme (Fig. 1) was reaction between a tetracyclic α , β -unsaturated ketone (I) and an appropriate nitro compound (II) to get an adduct (III)

* Basudev Banerjee Memorial Lecture, 1969.

1. L. F. Fieser and M. Fieser, "Steroids", Reinhold Publishing Corp., New York, 1959.
2. Y. Mazur, N. Danieli and F. Sondheimer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5889.
3. K. Schreiber, 'The Alkaloids', Vol. X, p. 1, (1967). Edited by Manske.

having functional groups suitably juxtaposed for elaboration to the desired structures. As four new asymmetric centres, at carbon atoms, 17, 20, 22 and 25, are generated in the Michael adduct and a fifth one arises at C-16 later in the sequence, the steric aspect of the project may seem formidable. This prospect was carefully analysed and stereochemical direction of the synthesis seemed feasible as discussed below :

Control of stereochemistry at C-25, was envisaged by use of resolved addenda (IIa or IIb) with appropriate configuration at C-2'. On basis of rear side attack in the final protonation step of Michael addition, the desired R configuration was expected at C-17. Further, equilibration could also be invoked since this disposition of the side chain is known to be preferred thermodynamically⁴. Again on basis of rear side attack the requisite S configuration at C-20 should obtain in the addition provided *cis*-isomer (C-20 methyl towards the nucleus) of I is employed. In synthesis of spirostanes and spirostanes the chirality at C-22 was to be destroyed in a later step and subsequent interlocking was expected to proceed in the desired sense on basis of known examples. Finally, C-16 carbonyl function, or its derivatives, could be expected to be attacked from the rear side by reducing agents and thus afford the desired stereochemistry at this point also. In essence then, the first phase of the problem resolved itself to : (i) synthesis of *cis*-isomer of ketone I from a totally synthetic compound, (ii) preparation of resolved addenda IIa or IIb, and (iii) development of conditions for control of Michael addition to I.

For synthesis of 5, 17(20)-pregnadien-3 β -ol-20-one, pregnenolone IV was selected as a relay material. It was readily available and its total synthesis was known⁵. Epoxidation followed by reaction with hydrazine⁶⁻⁹ gave a mixture consisting of a pyrazole and two allylic alcohols (VI and VII) with very close R_f values. The pyrazole was separated by chromatography and the non-basic portion shaken with manganese dioxide. Under these

4. D. K. Fukushima and T. F. Gallagen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 196.
5. H. M. E. Cardwell, J. W. Cornforth, S. R. Duff, H. Holtermann and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 361; A. Butenandt and J. Schmidt-Thome, *Ber.*, 1938, **71**, 1487; 1939, **72**, 182.
6. Huang-Minlon and Chung-Tungshun, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1961, 666.
7. S. V. Kessar and A. L. Rampal, *Chemistry and Industry*, 1963, 1957; *Tetrahedron*, 1968, 887.
8. W. R. Benn and R. M. Dodson, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 1142.
9. R. Sciaky and F. Facciano, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1963, **93**, 1014.

conditions only one of the diols was oxidised and separation into VII and VIII was possible by chromatography on acid washed alumina.

As compared to VII the C-16 allylic hydroxyl group in VI is less hindered and should get oxidised more readily. The obtained ketone VIII could thus be presumed to be the required *cis*-isomer but confirmation was sought through NMR spectroscopy. For unequivocal assignment by this method the isomeric *trans*-ketone (IX) was needed. To this end, oxidation of the diol mixture (VI and VII) was attempted with stronger reagents which, however, resulted in oxidation of 3β -hydroxyl group also. The *trans*-ketone IX was finally obtained from diol X⁸ which underwent ready allylic oxidation in conditions in which diol VII was unaffected. The latter observation lends interesting insight into manganese dioxide oxidation of allylic alcohol as discussed below.

From models it can be seen that C-21 methyl group shields both the C-16 hydrogen and C-16 hydroxyl group to a greater extent in VII than in VI. Resistance to oxidation in VII could arise from steric hindrance preventing attack at either of these sites by the reagent. In case of the diol X, the C-16 hydroxyl group is still more hindered while C-16 hydrogen is relatively accessible. As oxidation of this diol proceeds readily, it seems that in manganese dioxide oxidation of allylic alcohols the critical step, which is sensitive to steric hindrance, is the abstraction of carbinyl hydrogen. The distance between nearest C-18 hydrogen and the 16-hydroxyl oxygen atom, as estimated from Dreiding models, is about 4 Å in the diol X and any steric acceleration of oxidation in this compound may be considered unimportant. This conclusion¹⁰ runs contrary to that part of Gritter mechanism which envisages association of manganese dioxide with oxygen and subsequent transfer of carbinyl and hydroxyl hydrogens to the *same* molecule.

In order to complete the series, the missing fourth diol XI was synthesised by reduction of the *cis*-ketone VIII. The stereochemistry of all the four isomeric diols and the two ketones was largely adduced from NMR spectral evidence. The relevant frequencies are

10. It is being assumed that stereoelectronic factor i.e., overlap between the incipient orbital at C-16 and the π bond, is not significantly different in oxidation of VII and X. R. J. Gritter, G. D. Gupre and T. J. Wallace, *Nature*, 202.

given in Table I (subscript a refers to acetates) and some features of special interest are discussed below.

TABLE I

NMR Spectra of Isomeric Diols and Ketones*

Compound	C-18 Methyl proton	C-20 Vinylic proton	C-21 Methyl proton
VI (X)	55		102, 109
VIa (X)	55		100, 108
VII (X)	46		101, 108
VIIa (X)	47		92, 99
VIIa (Y)	48		92, 99
X (X)	56		98, 105
Xa (X)	55		91, 97
XI (X)	63		100, 108
XIa (Y)	62		98, 106
VIII (X)	64	390	108, 115
VIII (Z)	47	397	88, 96
IX (Xi)	57	343	122, 129
IX (Z)	43	238	125, 132

* The spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer at 60 Mc/s. The numbers indicate resonance frequencies of protons expressed in c/s in direction of decreasing field strength relative to an internal TMS standard. X, Y and Z refer to CDCl_3 , CCl_4 and deuteriobenzene respectively as solvents. Subscript 'a' means acetate of the parent alcohol.

The down field shift of ca. 10 c/s in the position of C-18 methyl resonance, observed in VI and X as compared to VII has been attributed by Benn and Doddson⁸ to the deshielding effect of the 16β -oxygen in X and of C-21 methyl group in VI. In confirmation of this explanation a paramagnetic shift of about 17 c/s has now been observed in C-18 methyl absorption of the diol XI in which both the factors are operative. In fact in the diacetate XIa the C-18 and C-19 peaks coincide whereas in the diol XI the former appears 1 c/s lower field which is unusual in normal steroids.

It has been observed¹¹ that in the NMR spectra of ketones, a change of solvent from deuterio-chloroform to benzene causes a shift which is dependent on position of the absorbing proton relative to a reference plane perpendicular to the CO bond. In *cis*-ketone VIII the C-21 methyl protons which are behind the reference plane, show an upfield shift whereas the C-20 vinylic proton which is in front of this plane moves down field in changing from deuteriochloroform to deuteriobenzene. Converse solvent shifts obtain in the *trans*-ketone IX, thereby confirming the assigned stereochemistry.

The calculated molecular rotatory contribution for acetylation of 16β -OH group in the *cis*-diol XI is -24 as compared to literature¹ value of +64. A similar deviation but in the opposite direction, for acetylation of *cis*-diol VI has been observed by Benn and Doddson. Both the *trans*-diols VII and X exhibit the expected molecular rotatory contribution for

11. D. H. Williams and N. S. Bracca, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, 3127; *Tetrahedron*, 1965, **21**, 2021; J. D. Connolly and R. McCrindle, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1965, 379; T. Ledaal, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 1653.

acetylation. The deviation in the *cis*-series is considered to reflect distortion of ring D of 17(20)-pregnenes⁸ with this configuration.

After obtaining the *cis*-ketone VIII and establishing its stereochemistry, exploration of steric course of Michael addition to it was undertaken, first with a simple addendum-nitromethane. Kloetzel¹² has extensively investigated Michael reaction of nitro alkanes with α, β -unsaturated ketones. In the present case this addition proceeded readily in *t*-butyl alcohol containing one equivalent of potassium *t*-butoxide. At 35° the reaction was complete in less than 2 hours. A possible complication was *cis-trans*-isomerisation of the substrate prior to addition. However, by use of excess nitromethane it could be avoided as was evident from periodic t.l.c. examination of the reaction mixture. Apparently the rate of isomerisation by weakly basic nitromethyl anion is considerably lower than the rate of its addition to ketone VIII.

Under identical conditions, nitromethane addition to *trans*-ketone IX was much slower than addition to VIII. Even after 24 hours considerable quantities of unreacted *trans*-ketone IX were found in the reaction mixture. The adduct XIII obtained in this case differed from *cis*-ketone adduct XII in details of I.R. spectrum, melting point and specific rotation. I.R. spectra of the crude products revealed that predominantly one isomer was formed in each case, showing that the addition was highly stereoselective. In comparison, Beard *et al.* observed a degree of randomness in 1,4-Grignard addition to a similar system¹³.

The predicted stereochemistry in XII (R-configuration at C-17 and S-configuration at C-20) was established by correlation with bisnorcholelanic acid (XVII). The thioketal XIV from the acetate of XII was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride. The resulting amine XV was acetylated and desulphurised to obtain a product which was identical with amide XVI.

12. M. G. Kloetzel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2271 and subsequent papers.

13. C. Beard, J. M. Wilson, H. Budzikiewicz and C. Djerassi, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 269.

XVI obtained from bisnorcholelic acid (XVII). All the reactions in this sequence were expected to maintain stereochemical integrity at C-17 and C-20.

The possibility of obtaining adduct XII from *trans*-ketone IX was then investigated with a view to utilise the *trans* diol VII. It seemed feasible if the Michael reaction was carried under conditions of rapid substrate equilibration, provided the addition to *cis*-ketone VIII is sufficiently faster than the addition to the *trans*-ketone IX reaction of an equimolar mixture of VIII and IX with nitromethane in the presence of excess potassium *t*-butoxide was complete in less than 3 hours, as expected, and furnished a crude adduct which on crystallisation afforded pure XII. However, as no satisfactory method for obtaining the *trans*-ketone from diol VII was found, this side product could not be looped back into the synthetic stream.

The reason for considerable difference in rate of nitromethane addition to *cis* (VIII) and *trans* (IX) ketones is not clear specially in view of equal rates observed in addition of amines to *cis* and *trans* crotono-nitriles¹⁴. From models, C-20 seems equally accessible to an addendum from the rear side in both the isomers. Further, each of these unsaturated ketones can be isomerised with base to a roughly equimolar mixture, showing them to be of comparable stability. The observed rate variation, therefore, is not likely to arise from differential relief of steric strain. It can, however, be rationalised in terms of a stabilising interaction in the transition state for addition to *cis*-ketone as shown in XIX. Such stabilisation may not be available in case of addition to the *trans*-ketone as necessary orientation of the side chain forces the C-18 and C-21 methyl group too close to each other. The stabilising interaction may be an attraction between the partial positive charge of nitrogen and the developing negative charge on oxygen or it may be an overlap of some orbital of the addendum with an orbital of the C-17, C-16, oxygen system. In any case, this explanation of rate difference requires substantial rotation of the C-17, C-20 bond when the transition state is reached. It is interesting to note that a recent kinetic study¹⁵ of Michael reaction reveals abnormally high negative entropy of activation which is construed to indicate some sort of cyclic interaction in the transition state.

An alternate explanation of the rate difference can be that on purely steric grounds the most favourable orientations for the bulkiest group (nitromethyl) attached to C-20 are

14. M. Friedman and Joseph, S. Wall, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2888.

15. John A. Markisz and Joseph D. Gettler, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 1965.

the ones shown in XIX and XX. Again, in transition state for addition to the *trans*-ketone such an arrangement would be opposed by steric interaction between C-18 and C-21 methyl groups.

In order to clarify the situation addition of cyanide ion to the two isomeric ketones (VIII and IX) was studied. Cyanide group is linear and as such would not exert steric effect (provided it is not highly solvated in the transition state). Further, it does not have a positive centre for ionic attraction with negative charge on oxygen. Here again two different adducts were obtained and the addition to *cis*-ketone was much faster.

To see if unsaturated bonds having π orbitals are necessary in the addendum for a stabilising interaction in the transition state, addition of dimethylamine to VIII and IX was also attempted. Under all the conditions which were tried, unfortunately, extensive *cis-trans* isomerisation occurred prior to addition. A similar difficulty arose in addition of *p*-tolyl mercaptan to VIII and IX. Interestingly, this reagent brings about rapid *cis-trans* isomerisation even in absence of added base, conceivably by free radical addition expulsion mechanism.

It was considered desirable to adduce some independent evidence for possibility of interaction between the functional group coming from the addendum and the carbonyl group of the substrate and recourse to spectroscopic methods was taken. It should be pointed out at the outset that conclusions drawn from adducts may not be strictly valid for the corresponding transition states, on which the rates depend, because of differences in charge of distribution and geometry. Such a study would only demonstrate the possibility of an interaction in the transition state. It may, however, have sufficient inherent theoretical interest also.

In the I.R. spectrum of nitro ketone XII both the carbonyl and nitro absorptions are slightly shifted as compared to those in XIII. This difference persists in their acetates. In the nitriles XXI and XXII, on the other hand, no significant shifting of cyano or carbonyl frequencies is observed. Sondheimer and Mazur¹⁶ have demonstrated a field interaction in C-16, C-22 dicarbonyl steroids with 20S configuration by I.R. spectroscopy. A number of cases, however, are known where no shift in I.R. frequencies is observed while an interaction between groups can be demonstrated by other means.¹⁷

Intensification of certain bands and other deviations from additivity have often been observed in adsorption spectra of molecules having non-conjugated chromophores suitably placed for coupling^{18,19}. In the U.V. spectrum of the nitroketone XII we found more than a twenty-fold increase in the extinction coefficient of the band in 283 nm region. In the isomeric ketone XIII this effect was less marked. Here a steric interaction between C-18 and C-21 methyl groups opposes that orientation of the side chain which places the nitro

16. Y. Mazur and F. Sondheimer, *Experientia*, 1960, **16**, 181.

17. G. P. Kugatova-Shemyakina and G. M. Nikolaev, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, **23**, 2987.

18. S. V. Kessar, Manmehar Singh and Y. P. Gupta, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1969, 583.

19. R. C. Cookson, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)* 1967; **A297**, 27; A. Moscovitz, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1967, **A297**, 40; H. H. Jaffer and M. Orchin, *Theory and application of ultraviolet spectroscopy*, p. 437, John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York, N.Y. (1962).

group nearest to the carbonyl function. The stereochemistry of these compounds seems specially conducive to interaction as the spectrum of the open chain model 5-nitro-2-pentanone (Y) is not anomalous (Fig. 5). In the shorter wave length region also the same order of absorption ($XII > XIII > Y$) was observed.

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

In going from ethanol to chloroform the 283 nm band in XII showed no appreciable solvent shift expected for a $n \rightarrow \pi$ transition (nitro or carbonyl). Either the ground and excited states are raised the same amount by change of solvent or neither state is effected at all. Perhaps the lone-pair electrons are less accessible to solvent due to proximate interacting group. Ultraviolet spectra of XII, XIII and Y taken in alkaline medium are shown in Fig. 6. In the long wave length region a maximum ($\epsilon > 1000$) is seen only in XII, although a small intensity increase is evident in XIII also. Since simple nitro alkane anions do not show any peaks in this region, the enhancement observed may be attributed to a carbonyl transition. From the point of view of explaining the difference in rate of addition of nitromethane to *cis* and *trans* ketones, the demonstration of strong interaction in the anion of XII is specially important as the transition state (XIX) for the addition step also has a unit negative charge.

Many aspects of theory of coupled chromophores, like the role of charge transfer states in intensification of $n \rightarrow \pi$ transition are not fully settled and examples with new features can be useful. In the nitroketone XII the chromophores are separated by more than three sigma bonds and, therefore, should be coupled directly²⁰. For such systems this seems to be the first example with dramatic intensity enhancement.

Usually strong $\Delta\epsilon$ values may be observed in CD when interaction between functions results in an inherently dissymmetric chromophore^{18,19,21}. The dichrograms of XII and XIII are, however, quite similar to those of similar C-16 oxosteroids²² which may be due to levelling of the nitro and carbonyl cotton effects.

Reverting to the synthetic scheme, 2-methyl-4-pentanoic acid (XXIII) was selected as a starting material for obtaining the required nitro addenda II. It was readily available from malonic ester and could be resolved by crystallisation of its quinine salt by the method of Stallberg²³. While optically pure S acid (XXIIIa) was available directly after nine crystallisations from acetone, partially resolved R acid was obtained from the first two mother liquors. Its further resolution with (+)-1-phenyl ethylamine²⁴ furnished R acid (XXIIIb) of about 90% optical purity.

Series a, R configuration at C-2

Series b, S configuration at C-2

20. Interaction involving central sigma orbitals is difficult to visualisé. (see ref. 19)

21. G. Snatzke, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 5002.

22. We are thankful to Dr. Snatzke for C.D. determinations.

23. S. Stallberg-Stenhagen, *Arkiv Kemi. Mineral. Geol.*, 1946, A23, 14; S. Stallberg-Stenhagen and E. Stenhagen, *ibid.*, 1947, B43, 6.

24. G. Stallberg, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1957, 11, 1430.

Two methods (Fig. 7) were used for elaboration of the above acids to the desired nitro compounds. In the first route the acid was esterified, reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and acetylated. Addition of HBr in presence of peroxide, gave a bromo acetate from which the nitro compound was obtained directly by reaction with sodium nitrite in DMF or better through iodide by conventional silver nitrite reaction. In each case the end product was contaminated by a closely boiling impurity which could be eliminated only by repeated fractionation. This material was identified as a nitrite from absorption at 6.1μ in the I.R. spectrum. Formation of substantial proportions of nitrite, especially with silver salt procedure, is unusual with primary halides. It seems that in the peroxide catalysed hydrogen bromide addition to the acetate considerable amount of a secondary bromide is also formed. When this addition was, instead, affected on the acid, no such difficulty was experienced. In this sequence subsequent reduction of ester moiety was carried with $\text{LiAlH}_4/\text{AlCl}_3$ to avoid reduction of the bromo function.

After having achieved the three preliminary objectives synthesis of desired end products was undertaken. Michael reaction of nitro acetate XXIVa with *cis* ketone VIII was comparatively slow, taking about ten days at room temperature for completion. The obtained adduct XXVI when subjected to a Nef reaction afforded a diketone XXVII which corresponded to kryptogenin in its physical properties. The yield, however, was low and no improvement resulted on use of modified conditions involving potassium permanganate. This failure could be attributed to steric crowding at C-22 or to internal aldol condensation of the formed diketone. To avoid the latter, it was considered advisable to reduce the C-16 keto group prior to Nef reaction. When the nitro ketone was refluxed with sodium borohydride in ethanol and the reaction mixture acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid a crystalline solid separated which, to our delight, turned out to be diosogenin (XXVIII). Its identity, as of all other synthetic products obtained in this work, was rigorously established by mixed m.p., t.l.c. and I.R. comparison with an authentic sample. Apparently, reduction

of the C-16 keto group, a virtual Nef reaction at C-22, deacetylation at C-27 and a double cyclisation had all proceeded in one operation. Efficient transformation of a nitro to carbonyl function at the hindered C-22 position is particularly gratifying in view of the difficulty experienced in effecting Nef reactions at sterically congested sites²⁵.

Starting with 2S-allyl propionic acid (XXIIIb) synthesis of yamogenin (XXX) followed on parallel lines. The adduct XXIX was obtained as an oil which on reaction with sodium borohydride readily afforded the sapogenin. Because 2-allyl-propionic acid of good purity was used for this synthesis, the 20% over-all yield of yamogenin from starting dehydro-pregnenolone may be taken as standard for this route²⁶.

I.R. spectra of crude products obtained by sodium borohydride reduction of uncrystallised adducts XXVI and XXIX do not reveal the presence of 20R sapogenins, and it may be concluded that Michael addition of XXIV to *cis*-ketone furnishes, primarily, products of 20S configuration²⁷. This may seem surprising as partial isomerisation of VIII to trans-ketone IX can be detected during the slow Michael addition. On basis of rear-side attack the latter should give a 20R product. However, the rate of addition to the *cis*-isomer (VIII) is expected, by analogy with nitromethane addition, to be much faster and, therefore, the main reaction should proceed *via* this even in presence of *cis-trans* isomerisation.

Synthesis of recently isolated isonarthogenin²⁸ was then undertaken to confirm its structure and to test the versatility of the developed synthetic route. The nitro compound XXXIV was prepared from 2-hydroxymethyl-4-pentenol-1-diacetate (XXXII) *via* peroxide catalysed hydrogen bromide addition. In reaction of the halides XXXIII with sodium or silver nitrite the product was again contaminated with a closely boiling nitrite impurity. Its elimination by repeated fractionation considerably reduced the yield. The alternate route, however, could not be used since, reduction of diethyl 3-bromo propyl malonate with lithium aluminium hydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride failed to afford the desired bromo diol.

Michael addition of nitro diacetate XXXIV to *cis*-ketone VIII furnished an oily product. By chromatography a solid corresponding to structure XXXV could be isolated from this material in low yield. However, the crude oil on reaction with sodium borohydride and work up gave, in good yield, a product identical with natural isonarthogenin²⁹ (XXXVII). The postulated intermediate, tetraol XXXVI, was expected to spiroketalise in such a manner as to place the C-27 hydroxymethyl group in the stable equatorial position.

This method was also employed for synthesis of cholesterol³⁰ 1-Nitro-isohexane (XXXVIII) was synthesised from the corresponding iodide by the usual procedure. Its Michael addition to VIII afforded XXXIX, which on Nef reaction lead to the diketone XL, in moderate yield. To eliminate the carbonyl functions a Wolff-Kishner reduction was carried but the I.R. spectrum of the crude product still revealed absorption in 6 μ region.

26. S. V. Kessar, Y. P. Gupta, R. K. Mahajan, G. S. Joshi and A. L. Rampal, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 899.
27. Isomerisation to 20S configuration during sodium borohydride reaction is not likely as the postulated intermediate keto-diol, is devoid of driving C-16, C-22 dicarbonyl interaction. Further, 20-isosapogenins if formed would not be expected to isomerise on contact with dil. HCl at room temperature.
28. H. Minato and A. Shimaoka, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.* (Tokyo), 1963, **11**, 876.
29. S. V. Kessar, A. L. Rampal and Y. P. Gupta, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 905.
30. S. V. Kessar, A. L. Rampal, S. Mangat and Y. P. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 501.

It was as such subjected to a modified Clemmensen reduction which resulted in disappearance of this absorption and chromatography on alumina afforded cholesterol (XLI).

Considerable difficulty was experienced in attempts to utilise the intermediate **XXVI** for conversion to steroidal alkaloids. It was reduced to an amino triol which was treated with Raney nickel in refluxing ethanol to bring about a double cyclisation through oxidation-reduction reaction. A tertiary amine was obtained, but in very low yield which could not be improved. Attempts to selectively protect 3β -hydroxyl group and convert the C-16

and C-27 hydroxyls to reactive derivatives for cyclisation with the amino function, were equally unrewarding. It may be pointed out that one is confronted with as many as five sensitive functions in these molecules and selective transformation present many difficulties. It was ultimately decided to use the nitro ester XXV in the Michael addition. Ester amino cyclisation would, hopefully, proceed under conditions not effecting some of the other functions and allow greater manouvreability. There was, of course, the danger of racemisation at the carbon atom next to ester grouping, during Michael addition. However, preliminary experiments had indicated that in presence of excess nitro alkane the reaction mixture is not sufficiently alkaline to bring about such an isomerisation.

Michael reaction of ester XXVb with *cis*-ketone VIII proceeded satisfactorily under the usual conditions. As the asymmetry at C-22 was to be retained in alkaloid synthesis special effort was made to separate the adduct into two expected C-22 isomers. By preparative t.l.c. with quintuple elution, both the nitro ketones (XLII and XLIII) were isolated in pure state inspite of very close R_f values. These were elaborated into solanidine and isosolanidine along the following lines.

Reduction of the nitro ester (**XLII**) with zinc and boiling acetic acid led to a neutral (ca. 65%) and a basic fraction. The neutral fraction itself was resolved into two products by thick layer chromatography. However, these were found to be **XLIV** and its 3β -acetate and for preparative purpose it was more convenient to hydrolyse the total non-basic fraction without separation. It is evident that during zinc and acetic acid reaction, reduction of nitro group, cyclisation to form ring E and a second cyclisation to form ring F had all proceeded as envisaged³¹.

31. S. V. Kessar, R. K. Mahajan, S. S. Gandhi and A. L. Rampal, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 1547.

The basic fraction XLV seemed to be a pyrroline from its I.R. spectrum. As this material could not be crystallised satisfactorily it was as such reduced with sodium borohydride. The obtained new base on refluxing with toluene furnished an amide identical with XLIV. Thus both fractions lead to the same amide and its combined yield from the nitro ester was 70%. Reduction of XLIV with lithium aluminium hydride in refluxing dioxane furnished solanidine (XLVI).

The isomeric Michael adduct XLIII when carried through the same sequence of reactions afforded a tertiary amine (XLIX), presumably 22-isosolanidine. Schreiber and co-workers³² have reported conversion of natural tomatid-5-ene-3 β -ol to 22-isosolanidine. On comparison the two products had similar m.p., I.R. spectra and R_f values. However, there was a definite depression in m.p. on admixture making their identity improbable.

It is known³³ that Δ^5 -22-isosolanidanone can be reduced to 5 α -22-isosolanidanones with platinum oxide in acetic acid while use of methanol as a solvent results in isomerisation at C-22. When base XLIX was reduced with platinum oxide in acetic acid, the crude product showed two spots on t.l.c., one of these corresponded to natural demissidine. The crude material was, therefore, further reduced with platinum oxide in methanol which lead to disappearance of the other spot and demissidine (L) identical with a natural sample was obtained. Direct reduction of XLIX with platinum oxide in methanol also afforded demissidine (L). Since isomerisation at positions only α to the tertiary nitrogen can be visualised

32. K. Schreiber and H. Ronsch, *Tetrahecon*, 1965, **21**, 645.

33. K. Schreiber, *Ber.*, 1964, 2368.

under these conditions, 22-isolanidine structure (XLIX) seems highly probable for our base. The possibility of it being isomeric with solanidine at C-16 is remote in view of the strain involved in trans-fusion of 5-membered rings. Yet the depression observed on admixture with Schreibers product, structure and stereochemistry of which is inferred in a logical way, seems difficult to explain and identity of our base as 22-isolanidine must be considered tentative. We have, nevertheless, been able to definitely establish that nitro esters XLII and XLIII differ only at C-22 by isomerisation experiments and by conversion of both to tomatid-5-ene-3 β -ol.

Lastly attention was diverted to elaboration of these Michael adducts to spirosolanenes. In the first step it was necessary to affect selective reduction of C-16 carboxyl group by a method which left the ester, nitro and Δ^5 -functions intact in XLII. Sodium borohydride seemed promising³⁴. However, under a variety of conditions even using urea/acetic acid for decomposition, only products devoid of nitro absorption in the I.R. were obtained. Evidently an abnormally facile Nef type reaction, probably dependent on proximity of carbonyl and ester functions, takes place during the sodium borohydride reduction or subsequent work up³⁵. It was, therefore, decided to avoid nitro anion formation altogether by carrying the reduction in acidic medium. Solution of sodium borohydride in water was slowly added to XLII in ethanol while the reaction mixture was maintained at a pH of 3-5 by concurrent addition of 3N sulphuric acid. On work up the desired nitro diol LII was obtained in excellent yield.

Reduction of the nitro group and subsequent lactam formation (LIII) proceeded smoothly when the nitro diol LII was refluxed with zinc and acetic acid. Further reduction of LIII with lithium aluminium hydride afforded an amino alcohol LIV which without further purification, was converted into its N-chloro derivative (LV). Subsequent treatment³⁶ with sodium methoxide in methanol, affected dehydrochlorination which was followed by spontaneous cyclisation. The obtained base was identical with natural tomatid-5-ene-3 β -ol (LVI). The C-22 isomeric Michael adduct XLIII also when carried through the above sequence of steps, afforded the same alkaloid³⁷.

34. H. Shachter, D. E. Ley and L. Zeldin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 3667.

35. Mechanism of this step is under investigation.

36. K. Schreiber and G. Adam, *Experientia*, 1961, **17**, 13.

37. S. V. Kessar, P. J. S. Bhatti and R. K. Mahajan, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1969, 603.

For synthesis of solasodine, methyl 5-nitro 2R-methyl pentanoate (XXVa) was synthesised. Its Michael addition to VIII was carried as in S series. The obtained product was again resolved into LVII and LVIII by thick layer chromatography. Since this separation was very laborious and the asymmetry at C-22 is ultimately eliminated in a subsequent step, unseparated mixture was carried through the sequence of steps used in S series, to obtain solasodine³⁷ (LXIII) as shown in Fig. 14. With this, formal total synthesis of all the three major structural types in steroidal sapogenins and solanum alkaloids was accomplished, although work on some individual members with distinctive structural features is still in progress.

In the end I express my gratitude to my students, specially Dr. A. L. Rampal, Y. P. Gupta, R. K. Mahajan and Manmehar Singh, but for whose hard work and steadfastness this project could never be completed. For facilities and generous help I am grateful to Prof. R. C. Paul, and for comparison samples to Prof. K. Schreiber and H. Minato. Also, I wish to acknowledge my deep debt to my teachers specially Prof. S. M. Mukherji and M. C. Kloetzel for initiation into research, inspiration and encouragement. My thanks are due to Drs. Sukh Dev, S. Selvavinayakam and G. Snatzke for help in determining some of the spectra. Lastly, assistance of Sh. Ahshok Kumar in preparing the material for this lecture is gratefully acknowledged.